

Innovative Approaches Are the Main Condition for Achieving Educational Efficiency

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Abstract. *In this article, a radical improvement in the education sector has become a requirement of the time, many laws are adopted that regulate relations in the field of education, non-governmental educational institutions are created, the appearance of educational institutions is formalized. The material and technical base is changing and improving, funding for scientific research and social support is increasing, including increasing the income of the teaching staff, creating separate state structures in the direction of innovation, creating new departments in higher education institutions.*

Key words: *Innovative approach, labor market, development, education, science, development of society, higher education, development of personality and society, reform, intellectual development, socio-economic development, non-governmental educational institutions "Education", law on education, continuous education, experienced specialists, scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel, research institutions.*

As the world civilization moves to a qualitatively new stage, an innovative approach to the implementation of various changes requires personnel to have high qualifications and be well-educated in all aspects. In order to meet the needs of the labor market, countries are looking at the development of education as a factor that determines modernization and the future, going the way of forming more professionally oriented types of education. In particular, the constructive dialogue between Uzbekistan and the UNESCO international organization regarding the reform of the higher education system is steadily developing. It is clear to all of us that the cornerstone of development and the force that makes the country powerful and the nation great is science, education and training. President of Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. [1]

Shiddat bilan rivojlanayotgan zamonaviy hayotni ilm-ma'rifat va ta'limning taraqqiyotisiz tasavvur etib bo'lmaydi. Jahonning yetakchi davlatlarida ta'limni rivojlantirish birinchi galdagi vazifa sifatida belgilanishi ham bejiz emas. Negaki, mamlakatning kelgusi ravnaqi aynan shu sohada qo'lga kiritgan yutuqlari bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir.

Today, in independent Uzbekistan, fundamental improvement of the education sector has become the demand of the times. Based on this demand, laws regulating relations in the field of education are being adopted. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" was adopted on September 23, 2020, and its purpose is to regulate relations in the field of education. Based on this Law, the main principles, educational system, types and forms of education have been clearly defined, the rules on distance education established in it, the necessary knowledge of students in accordance with the curricula and educational programs, It is aimed at obtaining qualifications and skills at a distance using information and communication technologies and the Internet worldwide information network [2]. Also, according to the Law, state higher education, secondary special, professional educational institutions and their branches, as well as state-participated higher, secondary special, professional educational organizations and their branches, by the decisions of the President or the

Government will be organized. It was determined that the establishment of non-state educational institutions will be carried out by their founders. Licenses for non-state educational organizations will be issued by the state inspectorate for quality control of education.

Of course, reforms in the higher education system constitute a certain part of the reforms implemented in the field of education.

In particular, to determine the priority directions of the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to raise the process of training independent thinking highly qualified personnel to a new level in terms of quality, to modernize higher education, based on advanced educational technologies. In order to develop the social sphere and economic sectors, the Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 No. PF-5847, serves as a prelude to new reforms in this field [3].

This document was based on tasks such as the development of integration of science, education and production in order to accelerate intellectual development, train competitive personnel, effectively organize scientific and innovative activities, and strengthen international cooperation. The content of the concept reflects the priorities of the reform of the higher education system of our country. It includes expanding the level of coverage and improving the quality of education in higher educational institutions, introducing digital technologies and educational platforms, attracting young people to scientific activities, forming innovative structures, commercializing the results of scientific research, achieving international recognition and other improvements. Plab clearly defined directions. All this serves to raise the educational process to a new level of quality.

Significant positive changes are taking place in the field of higher education of Uzbekistan during the period of independence. The appearance of educational institutions is changing, the material and technical base is improving, the financing of scientific developments and social support are being strengthened, including the income of professors and teachers. Separate state structures in the direction of innovation are being established, and new divisions are being opened in higher educational institutions. It is clear that all this will change the approach to higher education and increase its quality and level.

The socio-economic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan require the formation of a higher education system that will allow for fundamental quality changes in society and sustainable development in the near future. In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Parliament of December 28, 2018 [4], it is recommended to further strengthen the work aimed at creating wide opportunities for studying in the higher education system, increase the prestige of universities, increase the number of non-state educational institutions, and attract highly qualified personnel to the field and it was emphasized that one of the important tasks is to strengthen competition, strengthen cooperation with prestigious foreign institutes and universities, further increase the scientific potential of higher education institutions, and expand the scope of scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel training. The establishment of new higher education institutions in the regions, modern educational directions and specialties of personnel training, the opening of part-time and evening forms of education, and the increase of admission quotas are among the important tasks of the reforms in this regard.

The main goal of the fundamental reforms implemented in the education process today is to train mature specialists who are competitive in the conditions of market economy relations. It is for this purpose that during the years of independence in the field of education, a number of positive actions have been carried out in our country, and they, in turn, have begun to bear their positive fruits. It is a very positive thing that they are getting recognition. Attention is increasingly being paid to all-round support for talented young people with the intention of opening opportunities to realize their talents. This, in turn, has a wide range of purposes, such as the further development of the economy of our republic, which is finding its rightful place in the world community, the establishment of new modern production industries, the production of high-quality and competitive products for the domestic and foreign markets. is creating opportunities [5].

However, as in all times, the development of society is largely related to the potential of personnel. Therefore, continuous improvement of the educational process is considered one of the most urgent tasks in the management of society. After all, in any field, specialized personnel with high knowledge and skills and their ability to engage in effective research and development, create new types of products and introduce technologies into production are one of the factors that significantly affect the development of society. . Because mature personnel with such an opportunity, with their innovative ideas, not only create the ground for the development of science, but also play the role of an important intellectual factor for the development of economic sectors based on innovative requirements. Without it, no society can develop successfully at any time. It is especially important to take this into account in the context of unprecedented globalization processes, which are taking place as a result of the rapid development of information exchange tools and their becoming an integral part of the human way of life. In particular, the use of innovative technologies, modern pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. It can be said that this process has become an indispensable criterion for improving the quality and efficiency of education today. Therefore, on the basis of the same requirements, it is a necessary requirement of our time to increase attention to ensuring the quality of education and increasing its efficiency.

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